

The European Health Data Space (EHDS) is on the launch pad, with **interoperability as a key enabler** for seamless and secure health data exchange across Europe.

How will Europe manage training in digital health interoperability?

XiA, a groundbreaking initiative in digital health

The Xpanding Innovative Alliance (XiA) project is an **ambitious and relevant** European initiative that will **address the challenges of interoperability** in digital health with the advent of European Health Data Space (EHDS).

Through an innovative pedagogical approach, XiA aims to **bridge the skills gap in advanced digital health interoperability standards** among IT professionals, healthcare providers, and other implementers of the EHDS and European Electronic Health Record Exchange Format (EEHRxF).

XiA will make a **significant contribution** to build a **more efficient, integrated and citizen-centric European healthcare ecosystem**.

If you run a hospital or are a key player in one...

If you are an IT professional or IT provider...

If you want to anticipate all the steps to be EHDS-ready...

... Join us right now, and be part of XiA!

What XiA offers ?

XiA will set up **innovative training courses and pathways** and a **collaborative learning network** across Europe by 2028.

- ✓ **Modular training & micro-certifications tailored to individual needs** for flexible skills upgrading,
- ✓ **Open-source educational content** for free, long-term access,
- ✓ **European alliance** between universities, companies and public institutions.

Join the XiA Alliance!

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Check out our **website**
and follow us on **LinkedIn**

XiA's outputs

- 1** Leverage the large number of **educated workforce** and health and IT provider organisations in Advanced Interoperability Standards related to the EHDS requirements and future needs.
- 2** Develop a **comprehensive map of curricula and learning needs** combining technical and non-technical skills to build key competencies in Digital and Health Providers.
- 3** Create **engaging online educational content and immersive experiences** to strengthen networks of Alumni acting as cross-border change agents.
- 4** Establish a **structured schema for credentialing, accreditation,** and quality assurance to facilitate the reuse of XiA educational materials.
- 5** Integrate **digital transformation, interoperability, and cybersecurity skills** to ensure resilient health information systems across Europe.
- 6** Implement **micro-credentials and expand academic certification** through partnerships with European universities and key health networks.

Project overview

Project Name : **Xpanding Innovative Alliance (XiA)**

Duration : **48 months** | January 2025 - December 2028

Main objective : **Bridging the skills gap in digital health interoperability and establishing a sustainable and scalable educational framework**

Context and challenges : **The advent of European Health Data Space (EHDS) requires digital health professionals with advanced interoperability skills**

Method : **Create blocs of open source micro-courses** that can be **combined** in a most flexible way **into learning experiences or pathways fitting the needs of each stakeholder**, in educational institutions as well as in enterprise settings with certifications (ECTS, micro-credits)

Partners : **a consortium of 42 organisations** - universities, hospitals, SMEs, and industry leaders

Participating countries : **20 Countries** - Portugal, Norway, Germany, Finland, Greece, Slovakia, Spain, Italy, France, Ireland, Estonia, Belgium, Cyprus, Switzerland, Poland, United Kingdom, Austria, Slovenia, Lithuania and Canada

Budget : **3.981.700 €**

